

Position of Women in India- Pre and Post Independence

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Abstract

India is being known for respecting women and even worshiping as Goddess but the fact is that women in India have been ill treated and made to face in human condition at all level of her journey right from her birth. The origin of status of women can be traced to Manu in 200 BC. The women were not allowed to do anything independently even at her home and she could not take any decisions by herself whether its relating to her own self or any other family matters. However, there are many other circumstances which are common i.e. they are restricted at home, with restriction on their mobility and alone in seclusion.

Old and Awful practices are another major cause, which means women is always treated as home maker, house wife and to play the role that of a mother and wife. Though there are changes in such old practices in the rest of the world, such norms dominates in forefront in India and is successful in restricting rights and every other freedoms which are required to be given to the women. They are kept away from public forum and as a result in Indian politics the women's participation is hardly visible.

Keywords: India- respecting women- worshiping- ill treated- condition- journey- birth-status- traced-200 BC- not allowed- independently- home- decisions- relating- own self- family matters- circumstances- common- mobility- seclusion- Old and Awful- major cause- changes- dominates- forefront- successful- freedoms- required- public forum- women's participation.

Introduction

During Vedic period, whether equal rights were existing between men and women or not. But it was understood from the available sources that the attitude towards women were liberal and free policies and practices were prevailing pertaining to women were followed. There were practices whereby women were given the chance to actively participate in the religious and social work. Even the women were allowed to select their own life partner and a widow was permitted to remarry to another partner for better prospect .However, as India started growing and taking steps forward towards the civilization, growth and development, the social discrimination towards women increased in all its spheres.

During late vedic period, Jainism and Buddhism emerged as potent religious reform movements which brought with it many changes religiously. Jainism shared various prejudices caused to the women in its passages of canon and in the form of maxims. According to Buddhism, women's

Spiritual capacities were equivalent to that of men's. Religion of Buddhism began as to treat the women and men equal with respect to personal development by the following path of spiritualism. During early Vedic period the status of women were highly enjoyed and had slowly started diminishing during the late Vedic period. The male child were given more importance because he could be legal heir and legal representative of family property. Since the state saw steep increase in the economic and social status which sons started getting, it witnessed the position of women at a very declining state.

The age of Dharmashtras, the position of women reached an all time low. During this age wherein different codes of conduct, prescribed the various behaviour norms for women which were made and implemented. This period saw the exclusion of women from both economic and religious sphere. During the period of Dharmashastra many rituals started cropping in the Hindusim such as:

- a) Child marriage was encouraged.
- b) Widow marriage was looked down and they were not allowed to remarry.
- c) The birth of girl child was considered as a bad luck and therefore in order get rid of bad luck of the family, people went to the extent of killing the female child. Sati pratha came into existence and the said practice became wide spread. Women thought it was better to be sati then to suffer because of that women started burning themselves with the pier of the husband.

In Medieval India, the Purdah system which was prevalent among royal families, nobles and merchant class of people prior to the Muslims empire, started to spread to other class of people also. During the medieval period, the bad practices increased and they are follows:

- a) polygamy,
- b) sati,
- c) child marriage,
- d) ill treatment of widows.

Status of Women in Different Countries

In Pakistan, woman are deprived of their basic rights and their sufferings starts as soon as she comes to this world and more so even prior to her birth. Girl's fetuses are aborted every year in order to avoid the baby child. They think that girl child she invites problems to the family. There are some baby girls who survive all the odds and they become the one who are unwanted children. Such baby's life is filled with subordination with the male members who dominates them right from the beginning in each and every phase of their life. The most women of Pakistan has no right to make any decision may it be to decide on meal or for deciding her marriage and choosing the life partners. Before women were married they are under strict supervision of their father. Further they are always doubted in character especially when they go to school and communicates with other male students. Women are unable to make their choices about their life partner and therefore, their marriages are being decided and arranged by the family without concurrence of women.

Chinese women does enjoy a very admiring status in legal as well as society. Before 1949, china was a semi feudal and colonial state and therefore, there was lot of pressure of patriarchal system on the women however, the same was changed along with new foundation of China in 1949. Status of women of old china were not very admiring since they have no political rights as well they even had no society freedom. Women were absolutely dependent on their family for their financial needs, further they had no rights of inheritance and no right in the property. Women of china were not working and therefore they had no source of independent income. So they had no status as far as society is concerned. They were lead by father at their home and after marriage, they followed husband and in their last phase of life they were been lead by the son. Founding of New China saw various social movements and various law reforms could be seen.

The United States of America is a federation of fifty sovereign states. Therefore there were different practices being followed by all the States lacking uniformity in the laws and rules. The Constitution of United States has given limited powers to states to make laws concerning only to states. Whereas other laws such as property rights, inheritance, domestic relations concerning women lies separately with centre. Section 1 of the United States Constitution states that Citizens are the people of United States or any states that are born in the particular state or naturalized in the that particular state. Therefore, the state should not enact or implement the laws which are against the privileges granted to the citizens. Further, citizens shall not be deprived of their rights of life and liberty without following due process of law.

Arab women have not seen greater freedom or expanded rights since the beginning of Arabian countries. The survey results found that Egypt is the worst country to be a woman living in the Arab followed closely by the other countries Iraq and Saudi Arabia. There are Nineteen countries which signed the U.N. Convention to Eliminate All Forms of Discrimination against Women. In the survey the questions which were put to all the nations, were based on the said convention.

UK was no different from other countries with regard to oppression of women's rights. Women at the ancient cultures also were subordinated to men socially and legally. Women were treated inferior right from the human came into existence. All mention in documents, scriptures and some cases do justify inferiority of women to man.

In Ancient Greece, Athenian women were not allowed to avail the education further they were married at puberty to a grown up men without her consent. Women were considered and treated as the property of their family/fathers. Her family used to take all the decisions for them like marriage, divorce. Further also get them married to another person. In making all the decisions regarding women, women's choice are not taken into consideration at any stage.

Women at Canada has all the rights and protection available for the right development and protection for safeguarding their rights. Canada is a leader country which promotes and protects the women's rights and issues arising out of gender inequalities. In Canada, Central Government takes the responsibilities of making policies on all these issues. Canada is a nation which clearly understands as well as believes that equal rights to all is not only required for better human rights in the nation but also required for the sustainable development, social justice, peace, and security for all the human beings / citizens. Sustainable development in terms of security, peace and other can be achieved, only when women are given equal right to take part in development as well as decision making i.e. in politics. Various rights are enshrined and recognized in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW). Canada is a member of United Nations General Assembly. Further, 1981 CEDAW was ratified by Canada. After signing the said convention, it took lot of measures to make/ amend the laws and put in place various mechanism for implementing the laws and policies. After becoming the confirming party to CEDAW, it was governments responsibility to take the steps as per the standards set in CEDAW. Further strong mechanism is required for implementation. UN made lot of emphasis on promoting and safeguarding the women's rights and therefore, lot of progress could be seen in gender equality. After all these steps also, the struggle was yet to get over and go long way before achieving the ideal situation.

Modern India

When the arrival of British in India, the position of women saw many changes. The East India Company was mainly a trading company involved in trade in India. To expand their business, they started acquiring many territories and states in India. Since they started facing lot of issues while doing their own business of trading, the question of law and order in the acquired territories, posed

a great challenges before the East India Company. In order to handle the law and order situation, the company acquired the rights to make laws related to the crimes. Women were denied basic rights as well which included:

- a) equal matrimonial rights to property,
- b) rights to widows to remarriage,
- c) adoption and divorce rights,

Therefore, the 19th century is often termed as the century of social reform. The criticism by colonial authorities triggered anger among the people of India which had caused a serious threat to the ruling of colonial rule in India. Thereafter, it was declared by the queen that they will not be interfering in religious matters of the people of India. Status of women changed in all these years due to many reasons amongst environmental and institutional factors. Technological changes due to developing science created new roles which in turn have created new demands for the women labour.

Conclusion

Status of women changed in all these years due to many reasons amongst environmental and institutional factors. Technological changes due to developing science created new roles which in turn have created new demands for the women labor.

After independence though, the Indian constitution was drafted and many rights and freedoms were granted but the status of women had not improved. It only during 1954 and 1956 that, our parliament drafted many laws relating to Hindu marriage and divorce Act, succession Act, laws relating to Adoption, minority and guardianship Act were enacted and thereafter the women got equal rights as men and the status of women started developing. Old and Awful practices are another major cause, which means women is always treated as home maker, house wife and to play the role that of a mother and wife. Though there are changes in such old practices in the rest of the world, such norms dominates in forefront in India and is successful in restricting rights and every other freedoms which are required to be given to the women. They are kept away from public forum and as a result in Indian politics the women's participation is hardly visible.

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